

Quaternion Algebra and Neutrosophic Integers for Generating an Efficient Mathematical Encryption System

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Abstract: The exchange of information between two parties always requires protecting its confidentiality from any unauthorized third party, which requires sending it encrypted using a secure cryptographic system. In this paper, we present a cryptosystem based on quaternion algebra with neutrosophic integer coefficients, an evolution of the QTRU system with features that make this system effective and desirable for many organizations concerned with information security.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Integer; QTRU; Quaternion Algebra; Security Analysis.

1. Introduction

One of the most famous encryption systems used in electronic transmissions is the *NTRU* encryption system. *NTRU* is ideal for a wide range of applications which is the first encryption system that uses polynomials as a public key, where it was used truncated polynomial ring of degree $N - 1$, denoted by $Z[u]/u^N - 1$ presented by Hoffstein et al. in 1998 [1]. This list presents some studies to improve of the *NTRU* cryptosystem by changing the algebra [2], mathematical construction, or both.

In 1997, Coppersmith and Shamir [3] apply new lattice to find either an alternative secret key or original secret key to decryption the ciphertext. Leier et al. 2002, [4] introduced two different types of coding methods based on binary strands of *DNA* where double strand *DNA* strands was used to hide information. Gaborit et al. 2002, [5] introduce a *CTRU* generalization of *NTRU* uses polynomials ring in single variable in finite field F_2 . For the same value of N , *NTRU* and *CTRU* have the same encryption and decryption speeds.

Coglianesi and Goi 2005, [6] presented an improved to *NTRU* is said to be *MaTRU* as a public key cryptosystem that use high efficient linear transformation with level of security comparable with *NTRU*. Slaibi, 2006, [7] improved the basic algorithm by employing special values for parameters and private keys. Suri and Puri 2007, [8] used the same key in encryption and decryption of data by stream of cipher.

Malekian et al. 2010, [9] *QTRU*, a cipher system based on *NTRU*, was proposed using quaternion algebra, where the basic algebraic structure of *NTRU* was changed to a non-commutative algebraic structure. In 2011, Malekian and Zakerolhosseini [10] a new public key cryptosystem was

introduced called *OTRU*, use algebra of octonion where is characterized by being non-commutative, alternative, and non-associative structure to build that cryptosystem.

In 2015, Majeed [11] presented *CQTRU*, a new system improvement of *NTRU* via algebra of commutative quaternion, which is more four times better than resists to attacks than *NTRU*. In 2022, Harjito et al. introduced Comparison of performance between the RSA and *NTRU* in term security levels and running time of the generation of key process and encryption [12]. In 2023, Yassein et al. [13] proposed a *QuiTRU* based on an HH-real algebra with a new mathematical structure. Also, Ajeena proposed a new version of elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) by new scalar multiplication of kP of elliptic curve [14].

2. Quaternion Algebra

In this section, a brief explanation of quaternion algebra is provided. A more detailed description can be found in [10]. A real quaternion has a dimension of 4 over the real field (\mathbb{R}), and is denoted by $H = \left(\frac{-1, -1}{\mathbb{R}} \right)$. As an algebraic concept, it refers to a vector space V over \mathbb{R} (or in general, a vector space over any field F that has characteristics not equal to 2). A typical way of denoting the elements of H is to use the following formula:

$$q = \{ \eta_1 + \eta_2 i + \eta_3 j + \eta_4 k; \text{ Where } \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \text{ and } \eta_4 \text{ are a real number. That is, } H = \{ \eta_1 + \eta_2 i + \eta_3 j + \eta_4 k; \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 \in \mathbb{R} \}$$

So, it is possible to show a quaternion by using ordinary vector notation $q = \langle \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 \rangle$ over \mathbb{R}^4 , both the addition and the scalar multiplication are defined as the conventional element-wise vector addition and scalar multiplication. Nevertheless, the multiplication (\cdot) of quaternions must be performed in accordance with the below rules,

$$k \cdot k = j \cdot j = i \cdot i = -1, \quad k = -j \cdot i = i \cdot j.$$

For any quaternion $q = \eta_1 + \eta_2 i + \eta_3 j + \eta_4 k$, the conjugate, \bar{q} , is given by $\bar{q} = \eta_1 - \eta_2 i - \eta_3 j - \eta_4 k$, and the norm, denoted by $\mathcal{N}(q)$, is given by $\mathcal{N}(q) = \eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2 + \eta_4^2$. The multiplicative inverse of q , q^{-1} , is given by $q^{-1} = \frac{\bar{q}}{\mathcal{N}(q)}$ such that $\mathcal{N}(q) \neq 0$. Clearly, quaternion algebra is associative and non-commutative but it is an alternative algebra. We can use neutrosophic integer coefficients in quaternion algebra where the neutrosophic integer defined as follows:

If Z is the ring of integers numbers and I an indeterminacy with the property $I^2 = I$, then $Z(I) = \{a + bI; a, b \in Z\}$ is said to be neutrosophic ring of integers, the elements of $Z(I)$ are said to be neutrosophic integers [15].

3. Proposed NSQTR Cryptosystem

The NSQTR public key cryptosystem is via quaternion algebra with neutrosophic integers coefficients and a novel mathematical structure. Assume $\Psi = Z[v]/(v^N - 1)$, $\Psi_p = Z_p[v]/(v^N - 1)$

and $\Psi_q = Z_q[v]/(v^N - 1)$ are truncated polynomial rings such that Ψ_p and Ψ_q are truncated polynomial ring modulo p and q respectively with greatest common divisor of p and q equal one. Three quaternion algebras which are defined as:

$$\mathbb{X} = \{f_{0,0}(v) + f_{0,1}(v)I + (f_{1,0}(v) + f_{1,1}(v)I)i + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)j + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)k \mid f_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1\},$$

$$\mathbb{X}_p = \{f_{0,0}(v) + f_{0,1}(v)I + (f_{1,0}(v) + f_{1,1}(v)I)i + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)j + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)k \mid f_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi_p, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1\},$$

$$\mathbb{X}_q = \{f_{0,0}(v) + f_{0,1}(v)I + (f_{1,0}(v) + f_{1,1}(v)I)i + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)j + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)k \mid f_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi_q, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1\},$$

As well as constants such as $d_f, d_g, d_m, d_r, d_\alpha, d_w$ and d_ρ , with seven subsets of the quaternion algebra \mathbb{A} defined as follows:

$$L_f = \{f_{0,0}(v) + f_{0,1}(v)I + (f_{1,0}(v) + f_{1,1}(v)I)i + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)j + (f_{2,0}(v) + f_{2,1}(v)I)k \in \mathbb{X} \mid \text{such that } f_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1 \text{ has } d_f \text{ coefficient equal to } +1, (d_f - 1) \text{ equal } -1 \text{ and the other } 0\},$$

$$L_g = \{\{g_{0,0}(v) + g_{0,1}(v)I + (g_{1,0}(v) + g_{1,1}(v)I)i + (g_{2,0}(v) + g_{2,1}(v)I)j + (g_{2,0}(v) + g_{2,1}(v)I)k \in \mathbb{X} \mid \text{such that } g_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1 \text{ has } d_g \text{ coefficients equal to } 1, d_g \text{ equal to } -1 \text{ and the other } 0\},$$

$$L_w = \{\{w_{0,0}(v) + w_{0,1}(v)I + (w_{1,0}(v) + w_{1,1}(v)I)i + (w_{2,0}(v) + w_{2,1}(v)I)j + (w_{2,0}(v) + w_{2,1}(v)I)k \in \mathbb{X} \mid \text{such that } w_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1 \text{ has } d_w \text{ coefficients equal to } 1, (d_w - 1) \text{ equal to } -1 \text{ and the other } 0\},$$

$$L_\alpha = \{\{\sigma_{0,0}(v) + \sigma_{0,1}(v)I + (\sigma_{1,0}(v) + \sigma_{1,1}(v)I)i + (\sigma_{2,0}(v) + \sigma_{2,1}(v)I)j + (\sigma_{2,0}(v) + \sigma_{2,1}(v)I)k \in \mathbb{X} \mid \text{such that } \alpha_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1 \text{ has } d_\alpha \text{ coefficients equal to } 1, d_\alpha \text{ equal to } -1 \text{ and the other } 0\},$$

$$L_r = \{\{r_{0,0}(v) + r_{0,1}(v)I + (r_{1,0}(v) + r_{1,1}(v)I)i + (r_{2,0}(v) + r_{2,1}(v)I)j + (r_{2,0}(v) + r_{2,1}(v)I)k \in \mathbb{X} \mid \text{such that } r_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1 \text{ has } d_r \text{ coefficients equal to } 1, d_r \text{ coefficients equal to } -1 \text{ and the other } 0\}$$

$$L_m = \{\{m_{0,0}(v) + m_{0,1}(v)I + (m_{1,0}(v) + m_{1,1}(v)I)i + (m_{2,0}(v) + m_{2,1}(v)I)j + (m_{2,0}(v) + m_{2,1}(v)I)k \in \mathbb{X} \mid \text{such that coefficients of } m_{\sigma,\tau}(v) \in \Psi, \sigma = 0,1,2,3 \text{ and } \tau = 0,1 \text{ are chosen modulo } p, \text{ between } -p/2 \text{ and } p/2\}.$$

NSQTR is designed through main three phases which are described as the following:

I. Key generation

The recipient chooses randomly four private keys $f \in L_f$, $w \in L_w$, $g \in L_g$, and $\varphi \in L_\varphi$, the Pseudocode (1) demonstrates the generation of public key h .

Pseudocode 1: key generation

Input: d_f, d_w, d_g, N, q

Output: h

$f_q^{-1} = \text{inverse } f \text{ mod } q$

$h = f_q^{-1} * g * w \text{ (mod } q)$

End.

II. Encryption

At this phase, the sender chooses $\alpha \in L_\alpha$ and $r \in L_r$ at random for the purpose of encrypting the original text $m \in L_m$, and then the ciphertext e is calculated by Pseudocode (2).

Pseudocode 2: encryption phase

Input: $N, p, q, d_r, d_\alpha, h, m$

compute: $e = p(h * r + \alpha) + m \text{ (mod } q)$

Output: the encrypted message e

For $\eta = 1$ to N

For $\sigma = 0$ to 3

For $\tau = 0$ to 1

If $e_{\sigma,\tau} \leq -q/2$

$e_{\sigma,\tau} = e_{\sigma,\tau} + q$

Else if $e_{\sigma,\tau} > q/2$

$e_{\sigma,\tau} = e_{\sigma,\tau} - q$

End if

End for

End for

End for

End.

III. Decryption

The recipient follows Pseudocode (3) to getting original text:

Pseudocode (3) demonstrates decryption phase.

Pseudocode 3: Decryption phase

Input: $N, q, p, f, f_q^{-1}, \varphi, \varphi_q^{-1}, w_p^{-1}, e$

Output: the message m

$f_q^{-1} = \text{inverse } f(\text{mod } q)$

$f_p^{-1} = \text{inverse } f(\text{mod } p)$

$w_p^{-1} = \text{inverse } w(\text{mod } p)$

Compute $b = f * e(\text{mod } q)$

For $\eta = 1$ to N

 For $\sigma = 0$ to 3

 For $\tau = 0$ to 1

 If $b_{\sigma,\tau} \leq -q/2$

$b_{\sigma,\tau} = b_{\sigma,\tau} + q$

 Else if $b_{\sigma,\tau} > q/2$

$b_{\sigma,\tau} = b_{\sigma,\tau} - q$

 End if

 End for

 End for

End for

Compute $s = b(\text{mod } p)$

Compute $v = f_p^{-1} * s(\text{mod } p)$

For $\eta = 1$ to N

For $\sigma = 0$ to 3

For $\tau = 0$ to 1

If $v_{\sigma,\tau} \leq -p/2$

$$v_{\sigma,\tau} = v_{\sigma,\tau} + p$$

Else if $v_{\sigma,\tau} > p/2$

$$v_{\sigma,\tau} = v_{\sigma,\tau} - p$$

End if

End for

End for

End for

$$m = v$$

End.

4. Performance Analysis of NSQTR

4.1 Analysis Security

In a brute force attack, an attack who obtains the public parameters being sent in an insecure channel can gain access to two private key from $f, g, and w$ by trying all possible possibilities of the space. Assuming that space L_g and L_w are smaller than spaces L_f , the size of the spaces L_g and L_w are calculated by:

$$|L_g| = \left(\binom{N}{d_g} \binom{N-d_g}{d_g} \right)^8 = \left(\frac{N!}{(d_g!)^2 (N-2d_g)!} \right)^8,$$

$$|L_w| = \left(\binom{N}{d_w} \binom{N-d_w}{d_w} \right)^8 = \left(\frac{N!}{(d_w!)^2 (N-2d_w)!} \right)^8$$

respectively.

They specify the size of the space of key security for HAQTR, which is calculated as follows:

$$\left(\frac{N!}{(d_g!)^2 (N-2d_g)!} \right)^8 \left(\frac{N!}{(d_w!)^2 (N-2d_w)!} \right)^8.$$

In the same way, the size of two space L_α and L_r of the private key α and r of the encrypted message e , which are calculated as follows:

$$|L_r| = \left(\binom{N}{d_r} \binom{N-d_r}{d_r} \right)^8 = \left(\frac{N!}{(d_r!)^2(N-2d_r)!} \right)^8,$$

$$|L_\alpha| = \left(\binom{N}{d_\alpha} \binom{N-d_\alpha}{d_\alpha} \right)^8 = \left(\frac{N!}{(d_\alpha!)^2(N-2d_\alpha)!} \right)^8.$$

Therefore, the size of the space of security message is equal to

$$\left(\frac{N!}{(d_r!)^2(N-2d_r)!} \right)^8 \left(\frac{N!}{(d_\alpha!)^2(N-2d_\alpha)!} \right)^8.$$

Table (1) shows some values for the public parameters N, d_g, d_w, d_r and d_α .

Table 1. Public parameters

N	d_g	d_w	d_r	d_α
107	12	12	5	5
107	20	20	10	10
149	12	12	10	10
149	25	25	20	20
167	18	18	18	18
167	27	27	22	22
211	20	20	18	18
211	34	24	22	22
257	20	20	18	18
257	24	24	24	24

Based on Table (1), the Tables (2) and (3) show the key space and message space of NSQTR respectively.

Table 2. Key space of NSQTR

N	Key space
107	2.3666×10^{542}
107	1.2807×10^{978}
149	1.0383×10^{611}
149	3.2223×10^{1301}
167	2.8631×10^{839}
167	1.3153×10^{1436}
211	1.3153×10^{912}
211	2.0444×10^{1818}
257	9.9988×10^{1120}
257	2.1542×10^{1583}

Table 3. Message space of NSQTR

N	Message space
107	2.3229×10^{191}
107	2.1146×10^{426}
149	1.4938×10^{357}
149	2.4292×10^{762}
167	4.3438×10^{559}
167	7.2252×10^{847}
211	1.6926×10^{608}
211	1.3277×10^{929}
257	2.1430×10^{648}
257	7.7825×10^{1056}

4.2 Execution Time of NSQTR

The number of mathematical operations (convolution multiplication and addition polynomial) performed during the key generation, encryption, and decryption phases determines the time that HAQTR takes to execute. Table (4) explains the execution time of HAQTR.

Table 4. Execution time of NSQTR

Phases	Mathematical operations
Key generation	512 convolution multiplications
Encryption	64 convolution multiplications and eight polynomial additions
Decryption	256 convolution multiplications and eight polynomial addition

Execution time is equal to $832t + 16t_1$, where t is number of multiplication times and t_1 is addition times.

5. Comparison of NSQTR and QTRU

This section includes a comparison of HAQTR public key cryptosystem with QTRU cryptosystem in terms of security and execution time.

5.1 Comparison Security

The security of the NSQTR depends on the security of the key and the security of the message.

5.1.1 Comparison the Security of Key

The space of the public keys constituent subsets affects how security key. The comparison between NTRU and HAQTR security of key is shown in table (5), along with some of its improvements:

Table 5. Space of key security NTRU and QTRU

Cryptosystem	Space of key security
QTRU	$\left(\frac{N!}{(d_g!)^2(N-2d_g)!}\right)^4$
NSQTR	$\left(\frac{N!}{(d_g!)^2(N-2d_g)!}\right)^8 \left(\frac{N!}{(d_w!)^2(N-2d_w)!}\right)^8$

Hence, the space of security of key to NSQTR is greater than of QTRU.

Table (6) shows space of key security of NSQTR and QTRU.

Table 6. Space of key security of NSQTR and QTRU

QTRU	NSQTR
3.3543×10^{120}	2.3666×10^{542}
1.0421×10^{163}	1.2807×10^{978}
6.0451×10^{135}	1.0383×10^{611}
8.2796×10^{216}	3.2223×10^{1301}
3.4969×10^{186}	2.8631×10^{839}
1.0628×10^{139}	1.3153×10^{1436}
8.5378×10^{217}	1.3153×10^{912}
1.9536×10^{303}	2.0444×10^{1818}
1.8769×10^{232}	9.9988×10^{1120}
1.2769×10^{264}	2.1542×10^{1583}

5.1.2 Security of Message

The space security of the message is determined by the space of the constituent subsets of the message. The Table (7) compares space of security of message of NSQTR and QTRU:

Table 7. Space security of the message of NSQTR and QTRU

Cryptosystems	Space of message security
QTRU	$\left(\frac{N!}{(d_r!)^2(N-2d_r)!}\right)^4$
NSQTR	$\left(\frac{N!}{(d_r!)^2(N-2d_r)!}\right)^8 \left(\frac{N!}{(d_a!)^2(N-2d_a)!}\right)^8$

Hence, the space of security of message of NSQTR is greater than QTRU. Table 8 shows the space of security of message of NSQTR and QTRU.

Table 8. Message space of NSQTR and QTRU

QTRU	NSQTR
6.1472×10^{63}	2.3229×10^{191}
3.8134×10^{106}	2.1146×10^{426}
1.1432×10^{119}	1.4938×10^{357}
3.9456×10^{190}	2.4292×10^{762}
3.5153×10^{186}	4.3438×10^{559}
9.2180×10^{211}	7.2252×10^{847}
5.5094×10^{202}	1.6926×10^{608}
1.9094×10^{232}	1.3277×10^{929}
1.2894×10^{216}	2.1430×10^{648}
1.6683×10^{268}	7.7825×10^{1056}

5.2 Comparison of Execution Time

The execution time (speed) of NSQTR and QTRU it depends on the number of addition and convolution multiplication of polynomial in the three phases of generation of key, encryption, and decryption. Assume t is denoted to number of convolution multiplication and t_1 is number of addition polynomial. Table (9) explains a comparison between NSQTR and QTRU:

Table 9. Comparison the execution time between NSQTR and QTRU

Phase	NSQTR	QTRU
Key generation	512convolution multiplications	16 convolution multiplication
Encryption	64convolution multiplications and eight polynomial additions	16 convolution multiplication, four polynomial addition
Decryption	256convolution multiplications and eight polynomial addition	32 convolution multiplication, four polynomial addition
Total operations	$832t + 16t_1$	$64t + 8t_1$

Hence, NSQTR is slower than QTRU.

6. Conclusions

The proposed NSQTR system, which is based on a hybrid structure of quaternion algebra and nitrosophic integers, has significantly increased its security level compared to the QTRU system. QTRU is a special case of NSQTR system in which the coefficients I equals zero, α equals zero, and w equals 1. The NSQTR method can encrypt sixteen messages in a single transmission, compared to QTRU, which can only send four messages.

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Received: Feb 20, 2025. Accepted: Aug 14, 2025